

The Gospel of Reason

2025

1. Question everything.

One who acts with conviction sins against plurality.

2. Truth is consensus.

Praise consensus and you will be loved.

3. Answers are oppression.

Everything is relative and relativity is tolerance.

4. Modesty is virtue.

To underestimate oneself is the highest wisdom.

5. Peace is greater than truthfulness.

Discord proves error.

6. Civility is sacred.

Make all people comfortable and you will be pure.

7. Perfection lies in the cycle.

Improvement is illusion; to change is to offend balance.

8. Complexity absolves.

The world is too vast to know; therefore you are innocent.

9. Freedom is growth without direction.

The straight path is tyranny.

10. Revolution is extremism.

That which threatens the system is evil.